

Arctotis acaulis Renostergousblom

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 30 cm

Distribution:

Renostergousblom is distributed throughout the Western Cape and encroaches into the Northern Cape and Eastern Cape provinces. It is a common component of fynbos and renosterveld vegetation units.

Importance:

The species is endemic to South Africa and has contributed to hybrids that are grown commercially as ornamentals worldwide. It is common throughout the Western Cape and is a conspicuous and important component of fynbos and renosterveld. The availability of genomic information will facilitate molecular breeding of novel ornamental hybrid strains, gene mining, and the potential utilisation of bioactive compounds.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 51.5 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 25.41 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 2.21 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.5% [Single: 82.8%, Duplicated: 16.7%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 3 148.65 kilobases

Contig number: 1 811

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